

Curriculum Vitae

PERSONAL INFORMATION		
Full Name	Saadaq Mohamud Hassan	
Date and Place of Birth	01/11/1993, Mogadishu- Somalia	
Mobile No	+252611106632	
Email Address	Saadaqyare0120@hotmail.com	
EDUCATIONAL BACKGROUND		
PhD (Economics)	Ondokuz Mayıs University, Graduate School of Social Sciences, Department of Economics\ Turkey	2019-2023
Master Degree (Economics)	Ondokuz Mayıs University, Graduate School of Social Sciences, Department of Economics\ Turkey	2017-2019
Master Degree (International Business and Trade)	Samsun University, Graduate School of Social Sciences, Department of International Business and Trade \ Turkey	2019-2021
Bachelor Degree (Economics)	Ondokuz Mayıs University, Faculty of Economics and Administrative Sciences Department of Economics\ Turkey	2013-2017
Bachelor Degree (International Relations)	Anadolu University, Faculty of Economics and Administrative Sciences Department of International Relations\ Turkey	2016-2020
Secondary School	Maka-Almukarama Primary and Secondary School- Mogadishu-Somalia	2009-2012
WORK EXPERIENCE		
2014-2018	Internship at Kuveyt-Turk Bank\Turkey	
2019-2020	Volunteer Research Assistant At Ondokuz Mayıs University/Turkey	
2020-	Lecturer at different Universities- Mogadishu-Somalia	
AWARDS & SCHOLARSHIPS		
Turkey scholarships	2012- 2017	

ADDITIONAL CERTIFICATES		
Foreign Trade Education	Duzce University	2019
Product Management Program	İstanbul Business institute	2018
Management And Organization	Anadolu University	2019
Logistics Management	Anadolu University	2018
Project Writing and Management	Duzce University	2018
International Organization	Anadolu University	2020
PUBLICATIONS		
Published Scientific Articles		
<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. THE DEVELOPING TRADE RELATIONS BETWEEN TURKEY AND AFRICA IN THE LAST DECADE: THE CASE OF SOMALIA (<i>East African Journal of Business and Economics</i>) 2. A CAUSAL ANALYSIS ON FOREIGN TRADE AND ECONOMIC GROWTH: THE CASE OF SOMALIA(<i>International Journal of Scientific Research and Management (IJSRM)</i>) 3. DROUGHT EFFECTS IN SOMALIA AND SOLUTION PROPOSALS (<i>African Journal of Climate Change and Resource Sustainability</i>) 4. TRADE PERFORMANCE BETWEEN SOMALIA AND SOME MAJOR TRADING PARTNER COUNTRIES IN EAST AFRICA; PANEL GRAVITY MODEL(<i>Journal of Academic Value Studies (JAVStudies)</i>) 5. DROUGHT ANALYSIS OF SOMALIA USING DRINC SOFTWARE AND GIS-BASED ON RECONNAISSANCE DROUGHT INDEX (RDI) AND STANDARDIZED PRECIPITATION INDEX(SPI) (<i>African Journal of Climate Change and Resource Sustainability</i>) 6. COMPARISON OF SOMALIA AND THE EAST AFRICA COMMUNITY IN TERMS OF ECONOMY AND COMPETITION (Daha International University Academic Journal) 		
Scientific Articles Awaiting Publication		
<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 7. SOMALIA'S FOREIGN TRADE WITH GULF ARAB COUNTRIES: PANEL GRAVITY MODEL 8. ECONOMETRIC ANALYSIS OF ECONOMIC GROWTH, CURRENT ACCOUNT DEFICIT, UNEMPLOYMENT AND INFLATION IN SOMALIA AFTER TRANSITION FROM TFG TO OFFICIAL FEDERAL GOVERNMENT 		
COMPUTER PROGRAMS		
MINITAP	Excellent	OFFICE
		Excellent

R Project	Excellent	SPSS	Excellent
LANGUAGE SKILLS			
Mother Language	Somali Language		
Foreign Languages	Turkish, English, Arabic		
REFERENCES			
Selahattin KAYNAK	Prof. Dr.	selahattin.kaynak@samsun.edu.tr	
Ebül Muhsin DOĞAN	Prof. Dr.	emdogan@omu.edu.tr	
Miraç EREN	Associate Professor	mirac.eren@omu.edu.tr	